

Significance of Serum B Type Natriuretic Peptide P Levels in Cases of Acute Heart Failure with Maintained Ejection Fraction**B. Sravan Kumar¹, B. Suresh Reddy², Devasani Srinivasa³**¹Associate Professor, Department of General Medicine, Maheshwara Medical college and Hospital, Isnapur, Sangareddy, Telangana, India.²Associate Professor, Department of General Medicine, Maheshwara Medical college and Hospital, Isnapur, Sangareddy, Telangana, India.³Assistant Professor, Department of General Medicine, Chalmeda Anand Rao Institute of Medical Sciences, Karimnagar, Telangana, India

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Abstract:

Introduction: Heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) is prevalent, representing up to fifty percent of all heart failure (HF) cases and an increasing proportion of hospital admissions for acute decompensated heart failure. Alongside clinical severity, B-type natriuretic peptide (BNP), a peptide hormone produced by cardiomyocytes in response to elevated wall stress, is assessed in HFpEF patients. This investigation aimed to ascertain the importance of serum BNP levels in patients with acute heart failure and preserved ejection fraction.

Material and Methods: Sixty-eight cases with suspected clinical diagnosis of heart failure according to Framingham's criteria above 21 years of age were recruited. Participants went through transthoracic echocardiography and BNP testing done to diagnose the heart failure with preserved ejection fraction and classified according to diagnostic dysfunction.

Results: The BNP levels were over 400 pg/ml in 73.52%, between 100-400 pg/ml in 14.70%, and 11.70% had BNP levels below 100 pg/mL. A 2-D echo showed a left atrium measuring 38.98±4.34 cm, left ventricle measuring 43.11±5.60 cm during diastole and 26.76±3.90 cm during systole, and an ejection fraction of 57.21±3.20.

Conclusion: Serum BNP is an effective indicator for correlations when a diagnosis is difficult to establish. However, it is necessary to be knowledgeable about relevant issues in order to manage this sickness.

Keywords: Heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF), Left ventricular ejection fraction.

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Introduction

Heart failure is a clinical illness that affects 2-3% of people in the general population [1]. Its incidence is rising, and as a result of intricate treatment approaches, there is a greater chance of mortality, hospitalization, compromised quality of life, and financial load [2,3]. Signs and symptoms of heart failure and a left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) higher than 50% are characteristics of heart failure with preserved ejection fraction, also known as diastolic heart failure. This category is also often used to describe heart failure linked to moderate declines in LVEF (40% to 49%) [4]. HFpEF is becoming more widespread because of the rising number of patients with aging, hypertension, diabetes, and chronic renal disease. HFpEF is now linked to significant morbidity and mortality, constituting roughly 50% of clinical heart failure cases and often resulting in

hospitalization. Echocardiography is the definitive method for detecting heart failure; however, it is ineffective in obese individuals and those with a normal ejection fraction [6]. B-type natriuretic peptide (BNP) is the most often used laboratory assay due to its shown clinical value in the diagnosis and prognosis of heart failure, as evidenced by several research. BNP is a cardiac neurohormone released from the ventricles in reaction to increased ventricular volume and pressure overload. BNP values are recognized to be increased in individuals exhibiting symptomatic left ventricular dysfunction [7,8]. This research was conducted to assess the significance of serum BNP levels in individuals with acute left heart failure and maintained ejection fraction.

Material and Methods

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of General Medicine at Maheshwara Medical College and Hospital, Isnapur, Patancheru from January 2023 to August 2024. A total of 68 Cases with suspected clinical diagnosis of heart failure according to Framingham’s criteria attending department of general medicine and speciality clinic of cardiology above 21 years of age, with signs and symptoms of congestive cardiac failure, with left ventricular diastolic dysfunction and LVEF above 50% on transthoracic Echo and willing participate were included. Cases presenting LVEF Below 50% on transthoracic echo, with left ventricular dilation, with valvular heart disease and not willing to participate were excluded. Written informed consent was obtained from study participants and study protocol was approved by institutional ethics committee. All the participants were subjected to detailed clinical and physical

examination. Five ml of blood was collected and investigated and suspected heart failure patients went through transthoracic echocardiography and BNP testing done to diagnose the heart failure with preserved ejection fraction and classified according to diagnostic dysfunction. All such patients were subsequently submitted to detailed 2D/Doppler echocardiography. Ejection fraction was calculated by Modified Simpsons method. Left atrium volume index was calculated by using Simpson’s method for volume determination divided by body surface area. Mitral inflow velocity examination with pulsed wave Doppler was done in apical 4 chamber view by placing sample volume at tip of mitral valve leaflets.

The collected data was analysed by using SPSS version 26.0. Descriptive statistics was used to represent in frequency and percentages.

Results

Graph 1: Distribution of study participants as per BNP value

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical details of study participants

Parameters	Total no of cases	
	Frequency	Percentage
Age (In years)		
21-40	06	8.82%
41-50	11	16.17%
51-60	34	50%
>60 years	17	25%
Gender		
Male	28	41.17%
Female	40	58.82%
Diastolic dysfunction type		
Type 1	32	47.05%
Type 2	16	23.52%
Type 3	20	29.41%

Table 2: Comparison of study parameters with BNP levels.

Parameters	<100 pg/ml (n=08)	100-400 pg/ml (n=10)	>400 pg/ml (n=50)
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Hb (mg/dl)			
<10	05 (62.5%)	06 (60%)	34 (68%)
11-12	03 (37.5%)	03 (30%)	10 (20%)
>12	-	01 (10%)	06 (12%)
BMI (kg/m²)			
18-25	02 (25%)	04 (40%)	16 (32%)
26-30	05 (62.5%)	05 (50%)	24 (24%)
>30	01 (12.5%)	01 (10%)	10 (20%)
Status of hypertension			
Present	03 (37.5%)	03 (30%)	10 (20%)
Absent	04 (50%)	07 (70%)	40 (80%)
Status of diabetes mellitus			
Present	05 (62.5%)	06 (60%)	09 (18%)
Absent	03 (37.5%)	04 (40%)	41 (82%)
Status of dyslipidaemia			
Normal	08 (100%)	10 (100%)	33 (66%)
+Ve dyslipidaemia	-	-	17 (34%)
NYHA grading			
Grade III	08 (100%)	08 (80%)	22 (44%)
Grade IV	-	02 (20%)	28 (56%)

Table 3: Comparison of cardiac parameters with BNP in study participants.

Parameters	<100 pg/ml (n=08)	100-400 pg/ml (n=10)	>400 pg/ml (n=50)
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Left atrial diameter			
30-40 mm	07 (87.5%)	09 (90%)	16 (32%)
Above 40 mm	01 (12.5%)	01 (10%)	34 (68%)
E/A Ratio			
<1	05 (62.5%)	07 (70%)	20 (40%)
>1	03 (37.5%)	03 (30%)	30 (60%)
Diastolic dysfunction			
Type 1	05 (62.5%)	07 (70%)	14 (28%)
Type 2	02 (25%)	02 (20%)	18 (36%)
Type 3	01 (12.5%)	01 (10%)	28 (56%)

Table 4: Outcome of 2-D Echo and Doppler echocardiographic parameters among study participants.

Parameters	Outcome levels (Mean±SD)
2-D Echo	
LA	38.98±4.34
LVID d	43.11±5.60
LVID s	26.76±3.90
EF	57.21±3.20
Doppler Variables	
E velocity	1.05±0.33
A velocity	0.79±0.16
E/A Ratio	1.34±0.48
E/e Ratio	14.80±5.33

Discussion

Heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFPEF) is associated with high morbidity and mortality rates. According to current data, the number of patients with heart failure with preserved ejection fraction (HFPEF) is increasing over time, and hospitalization and death rates are

approaching those of patients with heart failure with decreasing ejection fraction [9]. According to Graph 1, 73.52% of study participants had BNP levels over 400 pg/ml, 14.70% had BNP levels between 100 and 400 pg/ml, and 11.70% had BNP levels below 100 pg/mL. The majority of

participants were between the ages of 41 and 50, with women comprising 58.82 percent.

Type 1 diastolic dysfunction was detected in 47.05% of patients, type 2 in 23.52%, and type 3 in 29.41% (Table 1). The left atrial diameter was more than 40 mm in 68% of patients with BNP >400 pg/ml, and 30-40 mm in 32%. The E/A ratio exceeded one in 60% of instances and was less than one in 40% of patients with BNP levels more than 400 pg/ml. We discovered type 1 diastolic dysfunction in 28% of the individuals, type 2 in 36%, and type 3 in 56%. A 2-D echo showed a left atrium measuring 38.98±4.34 cm, left ventricle measuring 43.11±5.60 cm during diastole and 26.76±3.90 cm during systole, and an ejection fraction of 57.21±3.20.

The Doppler scan showed diastolic dysfunction with E/A ratios of 1.34±0.48 and 14.80±5.33. Early filling velocity was 1.05 ± 0.33 m/s, whereas atrial filling velocity was 0.79 ± 0.16 m/s (Table 4). The BNP levels of patients with diminished left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) were found to be considerably greater than those with healthy left ventricular ejection fraction (HFVVEF) in a study of 615 individuals with mild to severe heart failure ($p < 0.001$) [10]. According to Verbrugge FH et al., cases with HFpEF and normal NP levels show obvious cardiac structural and functional abnormalities as well as hemodynamic features of HF, and critically, they are at a higher risk of mortality or HF hospitalization compared to patients without cardiac dyspnea [11].

Many studies suggest that abnormalities in biventricular (and atrial) function are more likely to signal a rise in HFpEF not isolated from left ventricular illness. Notably, among the most potent prognostic variables in HFpEF is right heart function [12, 13]. Over time, people with HFpEF often see their right ventricle get bigger and change shape. This can lead to more tricuspid valve regurgitation, swollen veins all over the body, and organ failure [14,15]. Santos AB et al. found that older people, having a lower peak LA strain, having more atrial fibrillation, and having poor LV and RV systolic performance are all linked to a lower peak LA strain.

This means that the LA isn't working right. It doesn't matter what other clinical factors might be present; LA dysfunction in HFpEF is linked to a higher risk of HF hospitalization. This link is not independent of LV strain or filling pressure, though [16]. \

A study by Issa O et al. found that people with HFpEF had higher levels of creatinine, body mass index (BMI), beta-blocker use, and Grade 2 diastolic dysfunction compared to a control group of people with high blood pressure.

According to echocardiographic studies, those with HFpEF had higher left ventricular mass index, E/A, and E/e', as well as higher right ventricular systolic pressures. In the heart failure group, most measurements of the left atrial (LA) changed, too. The LA-emptying fractions went down, and the maximum and minimum volume indices for the LA got bigger [17].

Conclusion

Serum BNP is an effective indicator for correlations when a diagnosis is difficult to establish. However, it is necessary to be knowledgeable about relevant issues in order to manage this sickness. The results showed that BNP and HFPEF were often correlated with diabetes mellitus, hypertension, left atrial diameter, and hypertension. Other comorbidities were obesity, dyslipidaemia, atrial fibrillation, and AF. The results show that serum BNP levels help with prognosis stratification, but further study is needed to find out whether people may benefit from better monitoring and more aggressive risk factor treatment.

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